

$bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^n$ AS A GRADED GROUP

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ABSTRACT. Let p be a prime. We calculate $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^n$, the connective unitary K -theory of the n -fold smash product of the classifying space for the cyclic group of order p , as a graded group using a Künneth formula short exact sequence for $n = 2$ and inductively for any $n \geq 2$. While this smashing is in progress some other spectra appear, for instance, the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^r$ for $r < n$. In order to producing a new homotopy equivalent to $bu \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^n$, we need to find a homotopy equivalence which simplifies the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^r$.

Keywords: The connective unitary K -theory; a Künneth formula short exact sequence.

1. Introduction

Let bu_* denote connective unitary K -homology on the stable homotopy category of CW spectra [1] so that if X is a space without a basepoint its unreduced bu -homology is $bu_*(\Sigma^\infty X_+)$, the homology of the suspension spectrum of the disjoint union of X with a base-point. In particular $bu_*(\Sigma^\infty S^0) = \mathbb{Z}[u]$ where $\deg(u) = 2$.

For a prime number p , in [4], we calculate the connective unitary K -theory of the smash product of two copies of the classifying space for the cyclic group of order p , $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge B\mathbb{Z}/p)$, using a Künneth formula short exact sequence, which is isomorphic to $bu_*(\bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} B\mathbb{Z}/p)$ in odd degrees and isomorphic to $\pi_*(\Sigma^2 H\mathbb{Z}/p[u, v, w]/w^{p-1})$ in even degrees.

In this section we shall merely introduce the Künneth formula sequence which implies our results, in case $n = 2$, upon taking homotopy groups.

In §2 we construct the maps which induce the isomorphisms in 1.3. Inductively, by replacing $B\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge B\mathbb{Z}/p$ by $(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, the n -fold smash product of $B\mathbb{Z}/p$, for $n > 2$, we derive a homotopy equivalence of spectra involving $bu \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, which in the left-hand side and other spectra appearing while this smashing is in progress, for instance, the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge r}$ for $r < n$. In order to produce this homotopy equivalence, we need to find first a homotopy equivalence which simplifies the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge (B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge r}$, and start with $r = 1$.

Following this homotopy and by a helpful corollary 3.6 in §3 we apply $\pi_*(-)$, the homotopy group, for this homotopy equivalence to compute $bu_*(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$ as a graded group for any prime p .

Let us fix some notations that we will use for this paper.

Notation 1.1.

- For $n \geq 1$, we write P_n for $(B\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\wedge n}$, the n -fold smash product of $B\mathbb{Z}/p$. In particular, $P_1 = B\mathbb{Z}/p$.
- For $i, j > 0$, we write $\Lambda_{i,j}$ for $2i + 2j - 2$.

Theorem 1.2. [4] For any CW-complex X , we have a natural exact sequence [which is called the Künneth formula sequence]

$$0 \rightarrow bu_*(P_1) \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p[u]} bu_*(X) \rightarrow bu_*(P_1 \wedge X) \rightarrow \text{Tor}_{\mathbb{Z}_p[u]}^1(bu_*(P_1), bu_*(X))[-1] \rightarrow 0.$$

Corollary 1.3. [4]

$$\begin{aligned} bu_{2*+1}(P_2) &\cong bu_{2*+1}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} P_1) \text{ and} \\ bu_{2*}(P_2) &\cong \pi_{2*}(\bigvee_{i=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{j,k>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p). \end{aligned}$$

In order to compute $bu_*(P_n)$ as a graded group we need to construct the maps which induce the above isomorphisms and inductively, extend these results to construct a spectrum which is homotopy equivalent to $bu \wedge P_n$ for each $n \geq 2$.

2. The homotopy equivalence

2.1. As we have just seen, by the Künneth sequence we can compute $bu_*(P_2)$, which is isomorphic to $bu_*(\bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} P_1)$ in odd degrees and isomorphic to $\pi_*(\Sigma^2 H\mathbb{Z}/p[u, v, w]/w^{p-1})$ in even degrees. In this section we will construct the maps which induce these isomorphisms. we will extend these results to construct a spectrum which is homotopy equivalent to $bu \wedge P_n$ for each $n \geq 2$.

Remark 2.2.

- $\bigvee_{i \geq 0} \Sigma^{ki} H\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq H\mathbb{Z}/p[v]$, where $\deg(v) = k$ and $\bigvee_{i=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{2i} H\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq H\mathbb{Z}/p[v]/(v^{p-1})$ where $\deg(v) = 2$.
- For $\deg(v) = 2(p-1)$, $\bigvee_{i=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{2i} H\mathbb{Z}/p[v] \simeq H\mathbb{Z}/p[u]$ where $\deg(u) = 2$. So $\bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j \geq 0} \Sigma^{2i+2j+2k+2} H\mathbb{Z}/p \simeq \Sigma^2 H\mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, u_2, u_3]/(u_3^{p-1})$, where $\deg(u_1) = \deg(u_2) = \deg(u_3) = 2$. We are not claiming any ring structure related to $\mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, u_2, u_3]/(u_3^{p-1})$, it is just a nice way to keep track of all the copies.

Lemma 2.3.

For a prime number p , there is a map $bu \wedge P_2 \rightarrow \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1$, which induces an isomorphism on homotopy groups in odd degrees.

Proof By [3], we have a homotopy equivalence $bu \wedge BS^1 \simeq \bigvee_{n>0} bu \wedge S^{2n}$. Denote by $\rho : bu \wedge BS^1 \rightarrow \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1$ the projection. Therefore we can construct the required map by the composition of the following maps

$$bu \wedge P_2 \xrightarrow{bu \wedge \alpha} bu \wedge BS^1 \wedge P_1 \xrightarrow{\rho \wedge P_1} \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1,$$

where $\alpha : B\mathbb{Z}/p \rightarrow BS^1$ is the classifying space of the inclusion map $\mathbb{Z}/p \rightarrow S^1$.

Let $f_n : S^{2n+1} \rightarrow bu \wedge P_2$ represents the generator of $bu_{2n+1}(P_2)$, so we have a composition $F_n : S^{2n+1} \rightarrow bu \wedge P_2 \rightarrow \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1$ which represents the generator of $bu_{2n+1}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1)$, and this shows that the map $bu \wedge P_2 \rightarrow \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1$ induces an isomorphism in homotopy groups in odd degrees as in 1.3. □

For an abelian group G , we have $(HG)_n = K(G, n)$ for $n \geq 0$ where $K(G, n)$ is the *Eilenberg-MacLane space*. By [2, p.393], for all CW-complexes X and all $n > 0$ there is a natural bijection $T : [X, K(G, n)] \cong H^n(X; G)$, where T has the form $T([f]) = f^*(x)$ for $x \in H^n(K(G, n); G)$.

Lemma 2.4.

For a prime number p , there is a map $bu \wedge P_2 \rightarrow \bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p$, which induces an isomorphism on homotopy groups in even degrees.

Proof

Let $t = \alpha \otimes \beta \in H^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k}(P_2; \mathbb{Z}/p)$ and $g_t : P_2 \rightarrow \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p$, where α, β , respectively, represent generators of mod p cohomology of P_1 of dimension m and n such that $m+n = \Lambda_{i,j} + 2k$, and g_t represents t , where

$$H^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k}(P_2; \mathbb{Z}/p) \cong [P_2, \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p]$$

Let ψ be the composition of

$$bu \wedge H\mathbb{Z}/p \xrightarrow{\rho \wedge 1} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge H\mathbb{Z}/p \xrightarrow{\mu} H\mathbb{Z}/p$$

where $\rho : bu \rightarrow H\mathbb{Z}/p$ represents a generator of $(H\mathbb{Z}/p)^0(bu) \cong \mathbb{Z}/p$. The required map is the composition of the following maps,

$$bu \wedge P_2 \xrightarrow{bu \wedge (\bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} g_t)} bu \wedge (\bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p) \simeq \bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} bu \wedge H\mathbb{Z}/p \xrightarrow{\bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} \psi} \bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p,$$

and using 1.3, we see that this map induces an isomorphism on homotopy groups in even degrees. $\square$

By 2.3 and 2.4 we have the following result.

Theorem 2.5. For any prime number p , there is a homotopy equivalence

$$bu \wedge P_2 \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1 \vee (\bigvee_{k=0}^{p-2} \bigvee_{i,j>0} \Sigma^{\Lambda_{i,j}+2k} H\mathbb{Z}/p).$$

Remark 2.6. From 2.2, the homotopy equivalence in 2.5 can be written as

$$bu \wedge P_2 \simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i} bu \wedge P_1 \vee \Sigma^2 H\mathbb{Z}/p[u, v, w]/(w^{p-1})$$

where $\deg(u) = \deg(v) = \deg(w) = 2$.

Inductively, by replacing P_2 by P_n , for $n > 2$, we get another homotopy equivalence, where the left-hand side is $bu \wedge P_n$. While this smashing is in progress some other spectra appear, for instance, the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_r$ for $r < n$. In order to conclude this section by producing a new homotopy equivalence, we need to find first a homotopy equivalence which simplifies the spectrum $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_r$. Let us start with $r = 1$.

Lemma 2.7. For any prime p , $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1 \simeq \bigvee_{i>0} \Sigma^i H\mathbb{Z}/p$.

Proof Let $f_i : S^i \rightarrow H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1$ represents a generator of $\pi_i(H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1) \cong H_i(P_1, \mathbb{Z}/p) \cong [S^i, H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1]$, and let $f : \bigvee_{i>0} S^i \rightarrow H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1$ such that $f|_{S^i} = f_i$. We construct F as the composition of these maps

$$\bigvee_{i>0} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge S^i \simeq \bigvee_{i>0} \Sigma^i H\mathbb{Z}/p \xrightarrow{H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge f} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1 \xrightarrow{\mu \wedge P_1} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1.$$

Let g represents a generator of $\pi_j(\bigvee_{i>0} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge S^i)$, so $g : S^j \rightarrow \bigvee_{i>0} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge S^i$ and the composition

$$S^j \rightarrow \bigvee_{i>0} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge S^i \rightarrow H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1$$

represents a generator of $\pi_j(H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1) = [S^j, H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1]$. Thus the map F induces an isomorphism $F_* : \pi_{2k+1}(\bigvee_{i>0} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge S^i) \cong \mathbb{Z}/p \cong \pi_{2k+1}(H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1)$ for all k , and Whitehead's Theorem shows the required result. $\square$

Remark 2.8. For $r = 1$, smashing P_r with the Eilenberg-MacLane spectrum of the group $\mathbb{Z}/p$ gives a wedge of suspensions of this spectrum of the same group. This can be written also as $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1 \simeq \tilde{H}V_1$, where $\tilde{H}$ refers to the reduced case, $V_1 = \mathbb{Z}/p[\alpha_1]$ and $\deg(\alpha_1) = 1$. Next we will explain the corresponding result for $r \geq 1$.

Corollary 2.9. For $r \geq 1$, $H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_r \simeq \bigvee_{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_r > 0} \Sigma^{n_1+n_2+\dots+n_r} H\mathbb{Z}/p$.

Proof It follows by induction from the previous result that

$$\begin{aligned} H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_r &= H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_{r-1} \wedge P_1 \\ &\cong \bigvee_{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{r-1} > 0} \Sigma^{n_1+n_2+\dots+n_{r-1}} (H\mathbb{Z}/p \wedge P_1) \\ &\cong \bigvee_{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_r > 0} \Sigma^{n_1+n_2+\dots+n_r} H\mathbb{Z}/p. \end{aligned}$$

$\square$

Theorem 2.10.

For $n \geq 2$ and a prime number p ,

$$bu \wedge P_n \simeq \left(\bigvee_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i_1+2i_2+\dots+2i_{n-1}} bu \wedge P_1 \right) \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \Sigma^{n+i-1} HV_{n,i}$$

where $V_{n,i} = \mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{i+2}, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-i-1}]/(u_1^{p-1}, u_2^{p-1}, \dots, u_i^{p-1})$, $\deg(u_j) = 2$ and $\deg(v_j) = 1$ for all j .

Proof The proof is by induction on n , where the case $n = 2$ is considered in 2.5 and 2.6 and the result agrees with the above statement.

Now let us assume that the statement is true for $n - 1$. By 2.6 we have

$$\begin{aligned} bu \wedge P_n &= bu \wedge P_2 \wedge P_{n-2} \simeq \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2j} bu \wedge P_{n-1} \right) \vee \left(\Sigma^2 H\mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, u_2, u_3]/(u_1^{p-1}) \wedge P_{n-2} \right) \\ &\simeq \bigvee_{j=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2j} \left(\bigvee_{i_1, \dots, i_{n-2}=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i_1+\dots+2i_{n-2}} bu \wedge P_1 \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-2} \Sigma^{n+i-2} HV_{n-1,i} \right) \vee \left(\Sigma^2 HV_{2,1} \wedge P_{n-2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

By 2.2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-2} \bigvee_{j=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{n+i-2+2j} HV_{n-1,i} &= \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-2} \bigvee_{j=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{n+i+2j} HV_{n-1,i} \\ &\simeq \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-2} \Sigma^{n+i} H\mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, \dots, u_{i+3}, v_1, \dots, v_{n-i-2}]/(u_1^{p-1}, \dots, u_{i+1}^{p-1}) \end{aligned}$$

where the right side spectrum is equal to $\bigvee_{i=2}^{n-1} \Sigma^{n+i-1} HV_{n,i}$. And by 2.9, for $r = n - 2$, we have

$$\Sigma^2 HV_{2,1} \wedge P_{n-2} \simeq \Sigma^n H\mathbb{Z}/p[u_1, u_2, u_3, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-2}]/(u_1^{p-1})$$

where the right side spectrum is equal to $\Sigma^{n+i-1}HV_{n,i}$ when $i = 1$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} bu \wedge P_n &\simeq \left(\bigvee_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i_1+2i_2+\dots+2i_{n-1}} bu \wedge P_1 \right) \vee \bigvee_{i=2}^{n-1} \Sigma^{n+i-1} HV_{n,i} \vee \bigvee_{i=1} \Sigma^{n+i-1} HV_{n,i} \\ &= \left(\bigvee_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i_1+2i_2+\dots+2i_{n-1}} bu \wedge P_1 \right) \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \Sigma^{n+i-1} HV_{n,i}. \end{aligned}$$

□

3. $bu_*(P_n)$ as a Graded Group

3.1. In this section we are going to compute $bu_*(P_n)$ as a graded group, first for $p = 2$ and after that for any prime p . This calculations follow the homotopy equivalence in 2.10.

Notation 3.2. For $n \geq 2$ and $p = 2$, the homotopy equivalence which is in 2.10 can be written as

$$bu \wedge P_n \simeq \Sigma^{2(n-1)} bu \wedge P_1 \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \bigvee_{j_1, j_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} \Sigma^{2(n-i-1) + \Lambda + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} k_j} H\mathbb{Z}/2$$

where $\Lambda = 2j_1 + 2j_2 - 2$, see 1.1.

To compute $bu_*(P_n)$ as a graded group, we apply $\pi_*(-)$ for the previous homotopy. In [4] the graded group $\pi_*(\Sigma^{2(n-1)} bu \wedge P_1)$ is computed, which is non-zero just in odd degrees. So to complete this calculation we need to compute the homotopy group of the rest of the wedges of the above homotopy, that is, $\pi_*(\bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \bigvee_{j_1, j_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} \Sigma^{2(n-i-1) + \Lambda + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} k_j} H\mathbb{Z}/2)$.

Now we are going to introduce and prove a supporting corollary for this calculation.

Corollary 3.3. Let $X_*^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = \bigoplus_{i, j > 0} \pi_*(\Sigma^{2m + \Lambda_{i,j} + \sum_{a=1}^n k_a} H\mathbb{Z}/2)$, where n, m , and $k_a \geq 0$ and $\Lambda_{i,j}$ as in 1.1. Then, for $t, \ell \geq 0$

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell} > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_{2\ell+1}, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m+\ell}{n+1}},$$

and

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell+1} > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_{2\ell+2}, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t+1}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m+\ell+1}{n+1}}.$$

Proof Inductively, we will prove the first claim, in degree $2t$, and the analogous calculations for the other claims are similar.

Firstly,

$$X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{n+1}}$$

and analogously,

$$X_{2t+1}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m+\frac{1}{2}-\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{n+1}}.$$

So

$$\bigoplus_{k_1 > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{s=0}^{t-m-1-\sum_{a=2}^n \frac{k_a}{2}} \binom{s}{1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=2}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{2}}.$$

Then, inductively, if we assume that

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_\beta > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=\beta+1}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{\beta+1}},$$

then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{\beta+1} > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} &= \bigoplus_{k_{\beta+1} > 0 \text{ even}} (\mathbb{Z}/2) \binom{t-m-\sum_{a=\beta+1}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{\beta+1} \\ &= (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{s=0}^{t-m-1-\sum_{a=\beta+2}^n \frac{k_a}{2}} \binom{s}{\beta+1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=\beta+2}^n \frac{k_a}{2}}{\beta+2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can calculate that,

$$\begin{aligned} \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2 > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_3, k_4, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} &= \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2 > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\frac{k_1+k_2}{2}}{n-1}} \\ &= \bigoplus_{k_1 > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{s=0}^{t-m-\frac{1+k_1}{2}} \binom{s}{n-1}} \\ &= \bigoplus_{k_1 > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\frac{k_1}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}{n}} \\ &= (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{s=0}^{t-m} \binom{s}{n}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m+1}{n+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell} > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_{2\ell+1}, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} &= \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell} > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^{2\ell} \frac{k_a}{2}}{n-2\ell+1}} \\ &= \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell-1} > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^{2\ell-1} \frac{k_a}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}{n-2\ell+2}} \\ &= \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell-2} > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^{2\ell-2} \frac{k_a}{2}+1}{n-2\ell+3}} \\ &= \vdots \\ &= \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell-2\eta} > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^{2\ell-2\eta} \frac{k_a}{2}+\eta}{n-2\ell+2\eta+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

When $\eta = \ell - 1$, the right side is equal to

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2 > 0 \text{ odd}} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^2 \frac{k_a}{2}+\ell-1}{n-1}} = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\binom{t-m+\ell}{n+1}}.$$

This completes the proof. □

Lemma 3.4. Let $n_1 \geq 0$. Then

$$bu_s(P_n) \cong \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{t-n+j+i+2}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, n = 2n_1 \text{ or } n = 2n_1 + 1, \\ \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-n+2} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t-n+j+i+3}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, n = 2n_1, \\ \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-n+2} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t-n+j+i+3}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, n = 2n_1 + 1, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof If we apply homotopy groups to the homotopy equivalence in 3.2, we get

$$bu_*(P_n) \cong bu_*(\Sigma^{2(n-1)} P_1) \oplus \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n-1} \bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} X_*^{n-i-1, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1}}.$$

The factor $bu_*(\Sigma^{2(n-1)}P_1)$ is concentrated just in odd degrees, see [4], whereas the factor

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} X_*^{n-i-1, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1}}$$

is concentrated just in even degrees when $i = 1$ and in both odd and even degrees when $i > 1$. By 3.3, the result follows. $\square$

3.5. When p is odd we write bu for the connective unitary K-theory with p -adic integers coefficients where $bu \simeq \bigvee_{i=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{2i}lu$, and lu is called the Adams summand, $lu_*(\Sigma^\infty S^0) \cong \mathbb{Z}_p[v]$ and $\deg(v) = 2p - 2$. By [4] we have $lu_{2k(p-1)+2i-1}(\Sigma^\infty B\mathbb{Z}/p) \cong \mathbb{Z}/p^{k+1}$ for $i = 1, \dots, p - 1$.

For $n \geq 2$ and any prime p , the homotopy equivalence which is in 2.10 can be written as

$$bu \wedge P_n \simeq \left(\bigvee_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \Sigma^{2i_1+2i_2+\dots+2i_{n-1}} bu \wedge P_1 \right) \\ \bigvee \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \bigvee_{j_1, j_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} \bigvee_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n-i}=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{2(n-i-1)+\Lambda_{j_1, j_2} + \sum_{a=1}^{i-1} k_a + 2\sum_{a=1}^{n-i} \lambda_a} H\mathbb{Z}/p.$$

where $\Lambda_{j_1, j_2} = 2j_1 + 2j_2 - 2$, see 1.1.

And again to compute $bu_*(P_n)$ as a graded group for any prime p , we apply $\pi_*(-)$ for the previous homotopy. The graded group $\bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \pi_{2t+1}(\Sigma^{2i_1+2i_2+\dots+2i_{n-1}} bu \wedge P_1) \cong \bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \bigoplus_{j=0}^{p-2} \mathbb{Z}/p^{k+1}$ where $t = k(p - 1) + \sum_{\beta=1}^{n-1} i_\beta + j + i$ and $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p - 2$, which is non-zero just in odd degrees. So to complete this calculation we need to compute the homotopy group of the rest of the wedges of the above homotopy, that is,

$$\pi_* \left(\bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} \bigvee_{j_1, j_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{i-1} > 0} \bigvee_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n-i}=0}^{p-2} \Sigma^{2(n-i-1)+\Lambda_{j_1, j_2} + \sum_{a=1}^{i-1} k_a + 2\sum_{a=1}^{n-i} \lambda_a} H\mathbb{Z}/p \right).$$

Similarly, we need to introduce a supporting corollary for this calculation.

Corollary 3.6. Let $X_*^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \lambda} = \bigoplus_{i, j > 0} \pi_* (\Sigma^{2m+\Lambda_{i, j} + \sum_{a=1}^n k_a + 2\sum_{a=1}^\alpha \lambda_a} H\mathbb{Z}/p)$, where

n, m, α, k_a and $\lambda_a \geq 0$ and $\Lambda_{i, j}$ as in 1.1. Then, for $t, \ell \geq 0$

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell} > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_{2\ell+1}, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \lambda} = (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t-m+\ell-\sum_{a=1}^\alpha \lambda_a}{n+1}},$$

and

$$\bigoplus_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{2\ell+1} > 0 \text{ odd}} \bigoplus_{k_{2\ell+2}, \dots, k_n > 0 \text{ even}} X_{2t+1}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \lambda} = (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t-m+\ell+1-\sum_{a=1}^\alpha \lambda_a}{n+1}}.$$

The proof is similar to 3.3, where

$$X_{2t}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \lambda} = (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t-m-\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{k_a}{2} - \sum_{a=1}^\alpha \lambda_a}{1}}$$

and

$$X_{2t+1}^{m, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \lambda} = (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\binom{t-m+\frac{1}{2}-\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{k_a}{2} - \sum_{a=1}^\alpha \lambda_a}{1}}.$$

Remark 3.7. We write $\Gamma(k, t)$ for $\bigoplus_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{n-1}=1}^{p-1} \bigoplus_{j=0}^{p-2} \mathbb{Z}/p^{k+1}$ when $t = k(p - 1) + \sum_{\beta=1}^{n-1} i_\beta + j + i$ and $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p - 2$

By applying the homotopy group to the homotopy equivalence in 3.5, and by 3.6 we get the following result.

Theorem 3.8. *Let $n_1 \geq 0$. Then for a prime p ,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & bu_s(P_n) \cong \\
 & \left\{ \begin{array}{ll}
 (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n-j-1}=0}^{p-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i} \binom{t-n+j+i+2-\sum_{a=1}^{n-j-1} \lambda_a}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t, n = 2n_1 \\
 & \text{or } n = 2n_1 + 1, \\
 \Gamma(k, t) \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n-j-1}=0}^{p-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-2} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t-n+j+i+3-\sum_{a=1}^{n-j-1} \lambda_a}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, \\
 & n = 2n_1, \\
 \Gamma(k, t) \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/p)^{\sum_{j=0}^{n-2} \sum_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{n-j-1}=0}^{p-2} \sum_{i=0}^{n_1-1} \binom{j}{2i+1} \binom{t-n+j+i+3-\sum_{a=1}^{n-j-1} \lambda_a}{j+1}}, & \text{when } s = 2t + 1, \\
 & n = 2n_1 + 1, \\
 0, & \text{otherwise .}
 \end{array} \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.9. *Let $p = 2$ and $n = 5$, then by 3.3 we have*

$$bu_{2t}(P_5) = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^3 \sum_{\ell=0}^1 \binom{j}{2\ell} \binom{t-3+j+\ell}{j+1}}.$$

Similarly, we can calculate that

$$bu_{2t+1}(P_5) \cong \mathbb{Z}/2^{t-3} \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{\sum_{j=0}^3 \sum_{\ell=0}^1 \binom{j}{2\ell+1} \binom{t+j+\ell-2}{j+1}}.$$

For $t = 5$, we have $bu_{10}(P_5) = (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{69}$, the direct sum of 69 copies of $\mathbb{Z}/2$. And $bu_{11}(P_5) = \mathbb{Z}/4 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/2)^{106}$. whereas, in case $p = 3$, $bu_{11}(P_3) = (\mathbb{Z}/3)^4 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3^2)^4 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{25} = (\mathbb{Z}/3^2)^4 \oplus (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{29}$, and $bu_{10}(P_3) = (\mathbb{Z}/3)^{28}$.

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